

DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS AND PROSPECTS OF THE UZBEKISTAN INSURANCE MARKET

Yuldashev Akrom Kurbannazarovich

Deputy General Director of "MY INSURANCE" LLC

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219920>

Abstract

This article analyzes the indicators of the development of the insurance market as a result of the reforms regarding the development of the insurance market of our country today and offers suggestions on the development prospects.

Keywords:

Insurance market, insurance premiums, insurance contracts, insurance compensation, reforms in insurance activity.

In the years of independence, mature scientists who conducted research on the formation of the insurance market and the development of insurance activities of our republic are also contributing to the development of the sector with their research. Conducting scientific and practical research on the development of the insurance market, studying the stages of development in a gradual manner and coming to scientifically based conclusions indicate the importance of conducting research on the sustainable development of the insurance activity in the future.

In the competitive environment, the importance of the insurance market of our country is increasing year by year. One of the factors determining the development of the insurance market is determined by the share of insurance premiums in the volume of the gross domestic product. According to the information of the "New Frontier" organization, the "Insurance penetration" indicator, which is determined by the ratio of total insurance premiums to the GDP, is 6.35 percent in the world, and 0.35 percent in Uzbekistan [2].

The issue of gradually increasing the minimum amount of authorized capital of insurance organizations in 2020-2022 was emphasized in the decision No. PQ-4412 of 02.08.2019.

Also, the initial charter capital of the insurer must be formed by the founders at the time of obtaining the license and must not be less than the specified minimum amount. At least 90% of the charter capital is formed by the funds of the founders (participants). It is not possible to use loans, pledged funds and other borrowed funds.

Table 1

Step-by-step increase of the minimum amount of authorized capital of insurance organizations, in 2020-2022 (billion soums)

Types of insurance activities	Current value	From July 1, 2020	From July 1, 2022
Optional insurance:			
general insurance	7,5		
in the life insurance network	10	15	20
Compulsory insurance (in the general insurance or life insurance network)	15	25	35
Reinsurance only	30	35	45

The total charter capital of insurance organizations should be increased 2.4 times in 2019-2022 - from the current 0.8 to 1.2 trillion soums. In particular, gradually increasing the minimum value of authorized capital of insurers (reinsurers) will help in achieving such results.

According to paragraph 3.2 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 2019 No. PF-5635 On the implementation of the strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [3] in the "Year of active investments and social development", "Reform and rapid development of the insurance market" " issues were determined. According to him, attention was paid to the issues of approving the concept of reforming and rapid development of the insurance market of our country and developing a new version of the Law "On Insurance Activities".

The new version of the Law "On Insurance Activity" defines insurance activity as follows: "Insurance is the protection of the interests of legal entities or individuals by means of payment in accordance with the insurance contract, insurance coverage (insurance amount) by them in the event of a certain event (insurance event) , i.e. activities carried out at the expense of funds generated from insurance premiums paid by the insured, as well as from other funds of the insurer".

Also, "insurance (reinsurance) activity is the activity of professional participants of the insurance market related to the implementation of insurance. The participants of insurance relations regulated by this law are insurers,

insured persons, beneficiaries (Beneficiaries) and professional participants of the insurance market.

Insurance organizations that are non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan may operate as founders (participants) of legal entities that are professional participants of the insurance market in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As of 2021, the total income of insurance premiums is 3732.8 billion soums, while the highest amount of income corresponds to the city of Tashkent, while the lowest figure corresponds to the Syrdarya region. If we take an analytical approach to the data in the regions of our republic, over the years, insurance premiums have had a tendency to increase.

In conclusion, insurance activity is one of the strategic areas, and its development is becoming an integral part of our country's economy.

References:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, December 29, 2020. Official website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: <http://www.press-service.uz>.
2. Based on the information of the organization "New Frontier" of Great Britain. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com>.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 17.01.2019 No. PF-5635 on the implementation of the state program in the "Year of Active Investments and Social Development". <https://lex.uz/docs/4168749>

